

NEW LSE Open Access Policy

A simpler process to make more publications open access and meet the requirements of funders and REF, without impacting on authors' freedom to choose where they publish.

Policy Summary

- Authors must send a copy of their Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) for journal articles, conference proceedings, book chapters and monographs to LSE Research Online, on acceptance and no later than the date of first online publication: LSEResearchOnline@lse.ac.uk – unless the publication will be Gold OA
- Researchers will retain the copyright to their papers, but LSE will apply a non-exclusive Creative Commons licence to the AAM
- Journal articles, conference proceedings and book chapters will be made available immediately on publication. Monographs and edited collections can have an embargo up to 24 months and will only be made available following consultation with the author.
- For journal articles and conference proceedings the policy applies to papers accepted from 1 January 2025, for books and book chapters it applies to books contracted from 1 January 2026.
- Co-authors should be notified of the policy and researchers can opt-out of the policy if they wish using the [opt-out form](#).
- **Read the full [policy here](#)**

Context

- Conflicting funder and publisher policies place an increasing financial and compliance burden on institutions, researchers and support staff
- Over 30 UK institutions have adopted similar Open Access policies
- The new policy has been approved by SMC and will ensure we can continue to make LSE research accessible and reusable to a wide audience and maximise the impact of social sciences research.

What authors need to do for journal articles from 1 January 2025

